

ORGANIZATIONAL AND LEGAL ISSUES OF ENSURING ROAD SAFETY

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Abstract. The article discusses the reforms implemented to ensure the safety of road users, protect their rights and legitimate interests, and reduce the number of road accidents. An analysis of laws and regulations adopted in the field of road safety was conducted. Additionally, a partial comparative analysis of national and foreign legislation is presented.

Keywords: road traffic, road users, safety, violations, driver's licenses.

In recent years, ensuring road safety and fundamentally improving its organizational and legal framework have been among the main concerns of our citizens, authorized state bodies, representatives of the general public, and our society as a whole. In this area, issues such as ensuring the safety of road users, protecting their rights and legitimate interests, reducing the number of road accidents, radically reforming the system of driver training and issuing driver's licenses to citizens, further increasing the accountability of authorized state bodies, establishing legal foundations for innovations in the field, and eliminating legal gaps have become major problems facing our society.

The field of road traffic safety is regulated by the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Road Traffic Safety" [1], the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 172 dated April 12, 2022, "On Approving the Rules of the Road" [2], and other regulatory legal acts. Article 3 of the Law "On Road Traffic Safety" provides a legal definition of road traffic safety as "the state of road traffic that reflects the degree of protection of road users from traffic accidents and their consequences." However, we are clearly witnessing that these norms are not fully effective in law enforcement practice, as evidenced by the increasing number of road accidents year after year.

Therefore, it is no coincidence that within the framework of Goal 16 of the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026, tasks are defined for "reducing road accidents and fatalities by improving road infrastructure and creating safe traffic conditions, including the full digitalization of the traffic management system and ensuring broad public participation in work in this area" [3].

Furthermore, the 3rd goal of the "Additional Measures to Accelerate the Implementation of National Goals and Objectives in the Field of Sustainable Development for the Period up to 2030," approved by the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers No. 83 dated February 21, 2022,

Task 3.6 provides for "a twofold reduction in the number of road accidents by 2025, including accidents caused by pedestrians violating traffic rules"[4].

A videoconference meeting chaired by President Shavkat Mirziyoyev was held on February 11, 2022, to discuss measures for strengthening road safety [5]. The meeting highlighted the main urgent issues in road safety, including reducing the number of traffic

accidents and fatalities, reviewing and improving national legislation based on existing problems, enhancing the legal awareness, mutual respect, and knowledge of road users, ensuring inevitable punishment for serious offenders, and addressing the inadequacy of the current driver training and licensing system.

To find organizational and legal solutions to systemic problems in road traffic, the head of state issued directives to relevant state organizations and officials. These directives focused on priority areas such as reducing the number of traffic accidents and serious violations; ensuring inevitable punishment for infractions; improving the legal awareness, mutual respect, and knowledge of road users; enhancing the efficiency of driving schools; digitizing the road sector; improving road conditions and infrastructure; and organizing convenient and safe traffic conditions for both drivers and pedestrians.

We can observe various norms aimed at effectively ensuring road safety in the national legislation of foreign countries. According to Russian Federation law, individuals who violate road safety legislation may face civil, administrative, criminal, and other types of liability. The laws of the Republic of Kazakhstan, Germany, France, and the Russian Federation stipulate criminal liability for disobeying lawful orders of police officers, physically resisting them, or using physical force against them. Additionally, Swedish Traffic Rules mandate separat

In order to implement the tasks and directives given by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on strengthening road safety:

Firstly, in consultation with deputies, experts, and the public, it is advisable to develop a draft law on amendments and additions to the Law "On Road Safety" in accordance with international legal norms in this field, providing for the following: clarifying the powers of the Cabinet of Ministers, local government authorities, and specially authorized state bodies implementing state management in the field of road safety, namely the Uzbekistan Agency for Automobile and River Transport, the Road Construction and Maintenance Organization, and the State Road Safety Service of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, while avoiding duplication of responsibilities; ensuring digital traffic management and safety; addressing issues of rights and obligations of road users;

Secondly, it is necessary to introduce appropriate amendments to the Administrative Liability Code and Criminal Code, providing for increased penalties for serious traffic violations, including repeat offenses, and disobedience to the lawful demands of traffic safety inspectors;

Thirdly, it is essential to establish specific mechanisms for holding pedestrians and other road users administratively liable for traffic violations and ensure the inevitability of punishment;

Fourthly, it is necessary to further expand systems for automated traffic regulation, video surveillance, and recording of traffic violations, as well as other technical means that ensure high efficiency in timely detection and prevention of offenses, and control;

In conclusion, the large-scale reforms being carried out based on the New Uzbekistan Development Strategy for 2022-2026 and the National Goals and Objectives in the field of sustainable development for the period up to 2030 will certainly be effective in strengthening road safety.

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